

Stability Constants of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} -fulvic Acid Metal Complexes

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Log K values of fulvic acid metal complexes are evaluated at pH 4.0 and 5.5 by ion exchange technique.

Log K values for Cu-F.A. complex changes for 2.57 to 3.93 with change in pH from 4.0 to pH 5.5, however, the same value for Ni-F.A. complex are 3.19 at pH 4.0 and 3.23 at pH 5.5 which indicate that stabilities of Ni-F.A. complexes are not changed for change in pH. The log K value for Zn-F.A. complex changes from 2.99 at pH 4.0 to 4.16 at pH 5.5. The result of this investigation indicate that the log K values are not in accordance with Irving-Williams series and the following sequences $\text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+}$ at pH 4.0 and $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$ at pH 5.5 are observed.

The conditions which regulate the availability of metal ions to plant roots or to biological systems often depend on the relative stability of the soil organic matter metal combinations. A knowledge of stability constants of different soil organic matter metal complexes will be helpful in understanding the role of these compounds in such systems.

Fig. 1.

Himes and Barber¹ used two methods to determine the strength of binding of Zn by soil organic matter. In the first method they assumed that only one type of adsorption site existed and the chelation reaction followed a Langmuir type isotherm which could be extrapolated to give the complexing sites and with this presumption they obtained $\log K$ values 3.4–5.6 for organic matter Zn complexes. The second method involved equilibrating Zn between the soil and a soluble chelating agent. From this method $\log K$ values were calculated as 9–10.4. Broadbent and Ott² tried to assess the relative stability of Cu, Ba, Ca and Mg organic matter complexes by comparing the amounts of each of the metals removed by equilibrating with one symmetry of hydrogen ions. Symmetry value determinations showed fairly small differences in relative stability of these complexes and the order $\text{Cu} > \text{Ba} = \text{Ca} \geq \text{Mg}$ was observed.

The ion exchange method as developed by Schubert^{3,4} and applied by various workers⁵⁻⁸ in this field to study the stability of soil organic matter metal complexes, has been applied in the present study.

The equilibrium constant for metal ligand reaction may be written as

$$K = \frac{\lambda_0 - 1}{\frac{\lambda}{(Ke)^n}}$$

or

$$\log \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} - 1 \right) = \log K + n \log Ke$$

where λ_0 = distribution coefficient of the resin in absence of ligand

λ = distribution coefficient of the resin in presence of ligand

n = number of moles of ligand complexed per mole of metal

Ke = concentration of ligand.

λ_0 may be calculated from the equation

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\alpha_0 \cdot V}{(100 - \alpha_0)g}$$

α_0 = % of metal bound to exchanger

$100 - \alpha_0$ = % of total metal which remained in solution

V = Volume of solution

g = weight of cation exchanger.

λ , was calculated from the same equation in presence of ligand.

λ_0 and λ were measured after maintaining the solutions at constant temperature, ionic strength, pH, volume and weight of the adsorbent. The exchanger was previously saturated with electrolyte.

$\log K$ values n , the ligand/metal ratio were calculated by the least square method.

TABLE 1

Wt. of resin = 0.03 gm, Total volume of solution = 10 ml, Temperature = 30°

pH 4.0

Zn-F.A. complex

Concentration of F.A. $C \times 10^{-4} M$	$\log C$	α_0	λ_0	λ	$\log \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} - 1 \right)$	n	$\log K$
0.9412	-4.0263	94.10	5235	1792	0.2835	0.67	2.99
1.8825	-3.7254	84.33		1125	0.5630		
3.7650	-3.4242	77.12		843.3	0.7167		
5.6475	-3.2482	71.67		680.4	0.8257		
7.5300	-3.1232	67.12		597.4	0.9048		

Ni-F.A. complex

0.9412	-4.0263	97.25	11790	2699	0.5268	0.67	3.19
1.8825	-3.7254	89.01		1642	0.7910		
3.7650	-3.4242	83.12		1193	0.9485		
5.6475	-3.2482	78.17		952.8	1.0557		
7.5300	-3.1232	74.08		803.2	1.1354		

Cu-F.A. complex

1.952	-3.7096	88.56	2581	1764	-0.3160	0.73	2.57
3.904	-3.4085	84.06			-0.0895		
5.856	-3.2324	81.03			0.0418		
7.808	-3.1075	78.66			0.1402		
9.760	-3.0106	76.42			0.2144		

pH 5.5

Zn-F.A. complex

3.764	-3.4243	96.80	12104	5158	0.1293	1.19	4.16
5.646	-3.2482	93.92		3756	0.3465		
7.528	-3.1233	91.85		3003	0.4824		
9.410	-3.0264	90.01		2476	0.5901		
11.292	-2.9475	88.14		2013	0.7012		

Ni-F.A. complex

1.952	-3.7096	89.43	2820	1522	-0.0696	0.83	3.23
3.904	-3.4085	82.04		1178	0.1440		
5.856	-3.2324	77.93		907.3	0.3228		
7.808	-3.1075	73.13		745.5	0.4445		
9.760	-3.0706	69.10		637.6	0.5844		

Cu-F.A. complex

1.952	-3.7096	94.01	5231	1878	0.2519	0.95	3.93
3.904	-3.4085	84.93		1172	0.5395		
5.856	-3.2324	77.85		842.5	0.7163		
7.808	-3.1075	71.65		668.6	0.8341		
9.760	-3.0706	66.73		553.8	0.9266		

The above relationship hold only to soluble complexes which are not bound to the cation exchanger.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fulvic acid (F.A.) was extracted from Chinsura soil (0-15 cm depth), fractionated and purified by standard procedure^{11,12}.

0 to 1.0 ml solution of fulvic acid was taken in 10 ml volumetric flasks in which 5 ml of (*N*) NaCl solution and 4 ml of different salt solutions viz., CuSO₄, NiSO₄ and ZnSO₄ were added. *pH* of these solutions were adjusted to 4 by 0.1 (*N*) HCl and the volumes were made to the mark. In a separate set *pH* of different solutions were adjusted to 5.5 by 0.1*N* NaOH solution. Known weights of Na saturated Amerlite (IR-120) resin were taken in 25 ml ground glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks. Solutions from volumetric flasks were transferred to these flasks and contents shaken for 6 hrs, allowed to equilibrate for 24 hr and the volumes of the solutions were made 50 ml. 10 ml of these solutions were titrated with E.D.T.A. solution with solochrome black indicator at *pH* 10 with ammonia buffer after decomposing the organic matters with H₂O₂ in alkaline media. Like the previous workers⁵⁻⁸ the final *pH* of the equilibrated solution were not noted, since there was no appreciable change in *pH*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average molecular weight of electro dialysed fulvic acid is found to be 840.¹¹

Compositions of Complexes : The molar F.A./Cu ratios at *pH* 4.0 and 5.5 are 0.73 and 0.95 respectively. Thus, at *pH* 4.0, three moles of F.A. complexed four moles Cu whereas at *pH* 5.5, three moles of F.A. approximately combine with three moles of Cu. The molar F.A./Ni ratios at *pH* 4.0 and 5.5 are 0.67 and 0.83 respectively. At *pH* 4.0, two moles of F.A. combines with three moles of Ni but at *pH* 5.5, four moles of F.A. react with five moles of Ni. The molar F.A./Zn ratio at *pH* 4.0 is same as F.A./Ni ratio but at *pH* 5.5 the F.A./Zn ratio changes to 1.20, showing six moles of F.A. reacted with five moles of Zn.

Stability Constants : The data used for calculations of log *K* values are given in Table 1 and in Fig. 1. It may be noticed from Table 1 that log *K* values of Cu-F.A. complex changes from 2.57 at *pH* 4.0 to 3.93 at *pH* 5.5, however, the same values for Ni-F.A. complex are 3.19 at *pH* 4.0 and 3.23 at *pH* 5.5 which indicate that stabilities of Ni-F.A. complexes are not changed for *pH* change. The log *K* value for Zn-F.A. complex changes from 2.99 at *pH* 4.0 to 4.16 at *pH* 5.5. The result of this investigation indicate that the order of stabilities of complexes formed between F.A. and a number of divalent metal ions, is not exactly in accordance with Irving-Williams series and the following sequences Ni²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Cu²⁺ at *pH* 4.0 and Zn²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ at *pH* 5.5 are observed. This disobedience of Irving-Williams series in the present study may be due to various factors of which nonhomogeneity of fulvic acid is considered to be the major one as in presence of strong cation exchanger (Na form of IR-120) possibility of the simple salt formation of the type M-F.A. (M = Cu, Ni or Zn) is very remote and the metal ion seems to be held up by the ligand by co-ordination or co-valent bonding. The present experimentally observed log *K* value for Zn-F.A. complex appears higher compared to the values 1.73 at *pH* 3.5 and 2.54 at *pH* 5.0 as reported

by Schnitzer *et al.*⁷. The log K values for Cu-F.A. complex is considerably lower compared to the values 5.78 at pH 3.5 and 8.69 at pH 5.0 obtained by these investigators, although the present stability constant values are almost comparable to that reported by Curpron⁹. Further though log K values of other F.A.-metal complexes are higher than those of humic acid (H.A.)-metal complexes at pH 4.0, the stability constant values of F.A.-Ni complex decreases compared to that of Ni-H.A. complex at pH 5.5. At the same pH log K value of Cu-F.A. and Zn-F.A. complexes are higher than those of Cu-H.A. and Zn-H.A. complexes. The stability of Ni-F.A. complex is maximum at pH 4.0 but with decrease in acidity the stability values become minimum which is quite opposite to the behaviour of Ni-H.A. complexes¹¹. The observed stability constant values do not provide any information on the mechanism of F.A.-metal interaction and on the chemical structures of the complexes formed.

The ion exchange technique as developed by Schubert based on mononuclear equation is less suitable for studying soil organic matter metal complexes. The organic matters extracted from different soils may form the central group or the ligand-metal combination may be polynuclear. The mole ratio as obtained from the slope of the plot $\log (\lambda_0/\lambda - 1)$ vs $\log C$ is not necessarily a function of the complex species formed but may depend on the particular experimental conditions. Rossotti and Rossotti¹⁰ also pointed out the defects of the ion-exchange method. Furthermore, the equation apply only to a single reaction and cannot be applied in cases where there is possibility of more than one reaction. It has been shown that acidic carboxyl, phenolic hydroxyl and amino groups react simultaneously with metal ions¹¹. So the log K values as obtained in the present investigation based on simple assumptions may not necessarily exactly follow the Irving-Williams series for stability constant of metal organic matter complexes.

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